

Literature Study Regarding The Description of Information System Analysis and Design (September 2021)

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Abstract—Information System is a combination of software, hardware, and telecommunications networks that people construct and use to acquire, generate, and disseminate meaningful data, primarily in organizational contexts. Information systems are used for a variety of purposes, including providing information to aid management decision-making, facilitating the implementation of daily operations, and providing appropriate information for parties outside the organization, particularly when it comes to management transparency. Information systems are designed to give information to all levels of management, including lower, middle, and top management. And there is four characteristics of Information System, such as New, Additional, Collective, and Affirmation. Manufacturing businesses can benefit from increased effectiveness and efficiency. Web-based apps can help to accomplish such improvements. One of these is PT X. They creates a joint venture with PT X, one of Indonesia's leading cement makers, in order to preserve its competitive edge. Several Process Laboratories are in charge of the quality assurance of the company's products. The first one is Process Laboratory IV is still relying on spreadsheet data. As a result, the majority of tasks and evaluations are still completed by hand. Slow information flow rates, minimal levels of information security, and the possibility for different types of fraud are still present. This study was carried out in order to develop a more efficient quality control information system through the use of a web-based application. Building: (a) Business process diagrams, (b) Use case diagrams, (c) Class diagrams, (d) Entity relationship diagrams, and (e) Databases, followed by web-based application design based on information system design findings. To reduce information security problems, the system architecture comprises four players with varying levels of power and access. Various types of fraud can be reduced as a result of these factors. Furthermore, by removing the need to re-input set point data, the system architecture enhances information flow efficiency. It can be stated that the use of web-based applications in the design of information systems has helped enhance efficiency and minimize the shortcomings of present information systems in the PT X.

Index Terms—Information, Management, Software, System, Quality.

I. INTRODUCTION

As life progresses, technology has increasingly become a fundamental necessity that is needed for all human beings. The human need for this technology is triggered by various factors,

one of which is the human need for information systems. Information systems have provided added value in process, production, management, quality, decision making, problem solving to competitive advantage which is certainly very useful for activities in an institution (Kadir, 2009). The role of information systems in various aspects makes it have a competitive advantage. The existence of this information system not only provides benefits for the environment itself, but also benefits its users.

Utilization of information systems can improve the quality of service of an agency, both in terms of speed and quality of information provided to manage or run the operations of an agency. If in its implementation, an agency has not implemented a computer-based information system in processing or operationalizing its work, then what happens is inefficient and not optimal work obtained. Operationalization of an agency using a manual system takes a relatively long time and can result in ineffective and inefficient output to be produced. This makes it important to apply information systems to a particular agency.

Thus, we can conclude if information systems and technology have an important role for humans in carrying out their lives. So that knowledge related to information systems becomes something that needs to be learned and also understood. One of the efforts that we can do in order to support human knowledge about information systems is to hold information system learning in formal education. The hope is that every human being has the provision of knowledge related to information systems. In order for the future all humans to get convenience with the existence of information systems and also technology in their daily lives.

II. STUDY LITERATURE

An information system's definition may be derived from the definitions of its constituent terms, namely systems and information. A system, according to Anggraini and Zega (2008), is a collection of numerous parts or elements that interact with one another to achieve a certain purpose. Jogiyanto (2005) uses the same concept, describing the system as a linked network of labor that performs an activity or achieves a specified objective. People, machines, things, and other sorts of entities may all be considered systems. In the

meanwhile, information is the outcome of processing data with a certain value or meaning. Leitch and Davis (2005) define an information system as a system that connects daily transaction processing needs, operating support, management activities, and strategies within an organization to provide the reports needed, both for internal and external purposes[3].

A. Components of an Information System

According to Stair (1992), computer-based systems (CBIS) in an organization are made up of the following elements[1]:

- 1) Hardware, which is a piece of hardware that allows you to enter data, process data, and output data.
- 2) Software, which refers to the computer's programs and instructions.
- 3) Database, which is a collection of data and information arranged in such a way that users of the information system may readily access it.
- 4) Telecommunications, or the communication that links system users and computer systems into a productive work network.
- 5) Humans, or information system personnel, are in charge of system upkeep and include managers, analysts, programmers, and operators.
- 6) Processes, i.e., procedures for using computer-based information systems that comprise strategies, policies, techniques, and rules.

B. Information Systems Types

Computer Basis Information Systems is often split into two categories of applications[1]:

- 1) A Transaction Processing System (TPS) is a computerized information system designed to process huge volumes of data in the course of everyday commercial transactions.
- 2) Management Information Systems (MIS) is a type of information system used at the management level to aid planning, control, and decision-making by supplying routine resumes and reports.
- 3) Decision Assist Systems (DSS) are information systems that integrate complex data and analytical models or data analysis tools to support semi-structured and unstructured retrieval at the management level of an organization. DSS is a decision-making system for businesses. A database, a graphical or mathematical model, and a user interface are the most common components of a DSS.
- 4) Expert System and Artificial Intelligence (ES & AI) is a knowledge representation that defines how a problem is approached by an expert. The focus of ES is on how to encode and modify knowledge from data (e.g., if....then rules).

C. Information Systems Application

Information systems are used for a variety of purposes, including providing information to aid management decision-making, facilitating the implementation of daily operations, and providing appropriate information for parties outside the organization, particularly when it comes to management transparency. The company's business plan must be supported by information systems. The ideal business process is the basis for the creation of information systems[1], because the

company strategy is implemented through a succession of business processes. Information systems are designed to give information to all levels of management, including lower, middle, and top management. The president, director (vice-president), and other executives in marketing, purchasing, engineering, production, finance, and accounting departments may make up top level management with executive management. Division and branch managers are examples of medium-level management. Foremen and supervisors are examples of lower-level management, often known as operations management[4].

D. Information Systems Function

Some of the functions of information systems in life are[2]:

- 1) Increase the accessibility of existing data effectively and efficiently to users, without the era of information systems.
- 2) Improve the productivity of system development and maintenance applications.
- 3) Ensure the availability of quality and skills in critically utilizing information systems.
- 4) Identify the need regarding information systems support skills.
- 5) Anticipate and understand the economic consequences.
- 6) Establish investments to be directed to information systems.
- 7) Develop an effective planning process.

E. Characteristics of Information Systems

The following are the characteristics of information systems in general[2]:

- 1) New, what is meant is the information obtained completely new and fresh for the recipient
- 2) Additional, it means that information can be updated or provide additional information to existing information.
- 3) Collective, what is meant is information that can be a personal correction of previous misinformation.
- 4) Affirmation, which is meant to be information that can confirm the information that already exists.

F. Example of Information Systems

The following are some examples of information systems[2]:

- 1) Aircraft referral system, used in travel agencies to serve bookings/ ticket purchases.
- 2) System for handling the sale of motor vehicle loans so that it can be used to monitor customers' debts.
- 3) Biometric systems that prevent people who do not want to enter confidential facilities or access confidential information by analyzing the fingerprint / retina of the eye.
- 4) Point of Sale (POS) system, applied by many supermarkets with the support of barcode readers to accelerate data entry.
- 5) Telemetry/remote monitoring systems that use radio technology, for example to obtain environmental temperatures on volcanoes or monitor the vibrations of railway bridge pillars.
- 6) Intelligent card-based system, can be used by medical personnel to find out the patient's disease history because the card is recorded data about the patient.
- 7) A web-based academic services system that allows students to obtain academic data or even be able to enroll in courses taken in the new semester.

8) An electronic data exchange system that allows electronic exchange of documents between companies and the data contained in the document can be processed directly by the computer.

G. System Development Life Cycle (SDLC)

The process of establishing how an information system (IS) can serve business needs, designing the system, constructing it, and providing it to users is known as the System Development Life Cycle. The systems analyst, who evaluates the business environment, finds possibilities for change, and builds an information system to implement the improvements, is a major player in the SDLC. Many people consider systems analysis to be one of the most intriguing, engaging, and demanding occupations available.

H. Rapid Application Development (RAD)

The term "rapid application development" (RAD) was used to characterize a software development method created and successfully implemented by the New York Telephone Co. Systems Development Center under the supervision of Dan Gielan in the mid-1970s. The sequential release approach is essentially a variant of RAD. It's also worth noting that certain technology vendors say that the development environment is advanced, citing high-end programming languages, application development tools, and supporting technologies as examples (CASE).

III. DISCUSSION

The following is the result of the discussion and also the comparison of information systems from the three reference journals.

A. Design of Quality Control Information Systems in Laboratory Processes IV PT X.

The purpose of this case study's research was to use web-based applications to build a more efficient information system. Four individuals with varying levels of authority and access are involved in the design's outcomes. These distinctions will improve information security, reducing the risk of various types of fraud involving data alteration by other parties. Furthermore, the information system's architecture removes the need for Operator 1 to do the same set point data input operations over and over again.

By eliminating these tasks, the time it takes to complete the full process is reduced, boosting system efficiency. Furthermore, by eliminating repetition, the risk of human and writing mistakes in the data input process is reduced. As a result, it can be stated that the use of web-based applications in the design of information systems has been able to enhance efficiency and mitigate the shortcomings of current information systems at the Process IV Laboratory of PT at this time.

B. Designing A Mobile Web-Based Island Tourism Marketing Information System

On the Pisang River in Padang, West Sumatra, this case study creates an island tourism marketing information system for Big

Dipper fisherman. The PHP programming language was used to create this marketing information system, which is powered by a MySQL database. Needs analysis, database system design, information system design, validation, and implementation are the steps that are completed. This mobile web-based island tourism marketing information system includes Pasumpahan Island, Sirandah Island, Pagang Island, Pamutusan Island, and Suwarnadwipa.

This marketing information system, in addition to presenting photographs of the tourist island's attractiveness, also includes a location map to make it easy for users. The design of this marketing information system is anticipated to enhance the number of visitors that visit the island, therefore helping the Biduk fishermen's income to grow in a sustainable manner.

C. Improvement of Warehousing Management Through The Implementation of A Warehousing Information System In CV ABB

Because the information system is being utilized for warehousing in this case study, it can be stated that the warehousing information system established in CV ABB has been fairly successful in suppressing the difficulties that have arisen in warehouse management thus far. Warehouse management becomes more accountable and transparent with CV. ABB's warehousing management information system.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the explanation above, we can conclude that A combination of software, hardware, and telecommunications networks that people construct and use to acquire, generate, and disseminate meaningful data, primarily in organizational contexts, is referred to as an **information system**. And there is 6 components of information systems, that is Hardware, Software, Database, Telecommunications, Humans, or information system personnel, and Processes. Information systems have 6 different types, that is Transaction Processing System (TPS), Management Information Systems (MIS), Decision Support Systems (DSS), and Expert Systems and Artificial Intelligence (ES&AI).

Information systems are used for a variety of purposes, including providing information to aid management decision-making, facilitating the implementation of daily operations, and providing appropriate information for parties outside the organization, particularly when it comes to management transparency. Information systems are designed to give information to all levels of management, including lower, middle, and top management. And there is four characteristics of Information System, such as New, Additional, Collective, and Affirmation. There is so many examples of the application of information systems in life that we can take, one of which is Aircraft referral system, used in travel agencies to serve bookings/ ticket purchases. Based on this, we can conclude that information systems are a very important need for humans to live in this digital era, because with information systems we will get convenience, effectiveness, and also efficiency in carrying out an activity.

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